

STRENGTH CHARACTERISTICS OF RECRON 3S FIBER REINFORCED CONCRETE OF DIFFERENT GRADES EXPOSED TO ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

PAPPU S. SOMAYAJULA BHARADWAJ

M.Tech, Department of Civil Engineering, Visakha Technical Campus, Andhra Pradesh
voletisnvlganesh@gmail.com

N. CHENNAKESAVA RAO

Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Visakha Technical Campus
sravs.chinnu5@gmail.com

DR. E.V.RAGHAVA RAO

Professor, Avanthi Institute of Engineering and Technology, Andhra Pradesh
evrrao@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT:

The concrete being widely consumed material in the construction industry has severe concern with the environment. The need of the time is to find some alternative material to save the environment.

The concrete has to sustain a very high temperature, when any fire accident occurs. The properties of the concrete are to be studied when exposed to the heat in order to understand effect of temperature on the concrete. Authors have presented the experimental results for the reinforced concrete of different grades at different temperatures.

KEYWORDS: Concrete, fiber reinforced concrete, strength.

1. INTRODUCTION:

The concrete when subjected to the high heat is experiencing the change in the properties. The effect of the heat is especially on the strength of the concrete. Fire incidences are very common in the residential buildings. The building when facing the fire is always subjected to the high temperature. The strength characteristics study is the scope of this paper. The experiment is carried out at different temperatures on the concrete fiber mixture material. The mixture is subjected to the very high temperature of 300 degree Celsius. The material selected for the experiment is of the grade M30 to M40.

General In general constructions of buildings in addition to the strength of the construction it should be able to withstand the damage causes by the fire. To avoid the rapid spread of fire which would cause both structural and human damage in addition to the concrete which we use some of the new admixtures has to be used.

Authors have performed the experiment on the fiber mixed concrete material for the period of the 56 days and the results are presented in the paper.

SCOPE OF WORK:

The present study is to investigate the effect of high temperatures on the properties of Conventional concrete by adding Recron 3s fiber. After casting, the moulds are cured in portable water tank for 7, 28, and 56 days. After curing, the specimens were removed and allowed for drying at room temperatures and some specimens were tested in room temperature and some specimens are kept in electric ovens and heated to different temperatures and for different exposure times. The parameters studied are

- 1) Elevated temperatures 150°C, 250°C, 300°C.
- 2) Exposure duration 1hr, 2hrs, 3hrs.

For M₃₀, M₃₅ and M₄₀ grades mix, Concrete cubes each of size 150x150x150mm and cylinders each of size 150mm diameter and 300mm height have been casted. Some of these casted specimens are tested at both room and high temperatures and after heating as per the prescribed temperatures the specimens are tested. To study the characteristics the recron 3s fiber was added to the concrete.

Fig.1: Recron 3S Fiber

2. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS ON MATERIALS:

The strength of the concrete is better understood by the carrying capacity of the load. Authors have carried out the test on the mixture in order to understand the results related to the strength of the mixture. 516-1959 IS standards are followed during the testing of the mixture.

COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH TEST:

The compressive strength of concrete was calculated using the following formula.

$$F_c = P/A \text{ Where,}$$

F_c = Compressive Strength

P = Maximum Load applied (Nw)

A = Cross sectional Area (mm²)

SPLIT TENSILE STRENGTH TEST:

The split tensile strength of concrete was calculated using the following formula:

$$F_s = \frac{2P}{\pi dl}$$

Where,

F_s = Split Tensile strength

P = maximum load (Nw)

d = diameter of the cylinder (i.e, 150mm).

l = length of the cylinder (i.e, 300mm)

The tests were carried out in the Muffle furnace as the testing needs the very high temperature to study the characteristics.

3. METHODOLOGY:

A mix design of M30, M35, M40 grade concrete was done according to the guidelines given in IS: 10262 - 2009. The samples are mixed with some percentages of 0.10%, 0.15% to 0.40% of the weight of concrete.

After the mixing the compressive strength and split tensile strength are conducted at high temperatures at different durations for 7 to 56 days.

The Mix Proportions are taken as below

Mix Proportions by Weight for M30:

Cement	Fine Aggregate	Coarse Aggregate	Water cement ratio
406.4kg	732.4kg	1167kg	178litres
1.00	1.80	2.87	0.438

Mix Proportions by Weight for M35:

Cement	Fine Aggregate	Coarse Aggregate	Water cement ratio
409.091kg	730.31kg	1163.36kg	180litres
1.00	1.78	2.84	0.44

Mix Proportions by Weight for M40:

Cement	Fine Aggregate	Coarse Aggregate	Water cement ratio
415.09 kg	732.43 kg	1167kg	176 litres
1.00	1.76	2.81	0.424

Terminology for Sample Mixes:

S.No	Sample mix name	Description
1	S ₁	M30 Grade Conventional Concrete
2	S _{M30}	Cement + Sand + Coarse Aggregate + 0.3% Recron 3S Fiber
3	S ₂	M35 Grade Conventional Concrete
4	S _{M35}	Cement + Sand + Coarse Aggregate + 0.3% Recron 3S Fiber
5	S ₃	M40 Grade Conventional Concrete
6	S _{M40}	Cement + Sand + Coarse Aggregate + 0.3% Recron 3S Fiber

TESTING PROCEDURE:

Remove the specimen from water after specified curing time. After curing of specimens tests were conducted on the cubes and cylinders. Cubes and Cylinders are tested at elevated temperatures 150°C, 250°C, and 300°C. Cubes are placed in oven. The temperature is controlled in the control panel in which the temperature can be set to required magnitude and can be maintained for the required time without any changes in the temperature. The specimens that were heated in the electric oven in such a way, until the required temperature and every side of the sample has to be exposed to temperature, the temperature is maintained constantly for a period of 1hour at 150°C. After exposing the samples to required temperature and for the required duration, the heating of the samples was stopped and was allowed to cool. After cooling, compressive and tensile strength are tested to the samples.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Variation of Compressive Strength results:

Fig 2. M30 Grade of concrete

Fig 3. M35 Grade of Concrete

Fig 4. M40 Grade of Concrete

Variation of Split Tensile Strength:

Fig 5. M30 Grade of Concrete

Fig 6. M35 Grade of Concrete

Fig 7. M40 Grade of Concrete

5. CONCLUSION:

The main objective achieved with this study is the study of the strength characteristics of the mixture. We have observed that when the mixture is subjected to the high temperature, the tensile strength is best with 19 to 22% of mixture is added with 81 to 78 % concrete. The observations are taken over the period of 56 days. The drawback of the mixture is low strength at the temperature above 300° C as Recron 3s get melts at 250° C.

REFERENCES:

- 1) Bureau of India Standard, "Indian standard concrete mix proportioning – Guidelines"
- 2) (First revision) IS-10262:2009, New Delhi, India.
- 3) Bureau of India Standard, "Code of practice for plain and reinforced concrete", fourth edition, IS-456:2000, New Delhi.
- 4) Indian Standard IS-12269:1987, "Specifications for 53 grade Ordinary Portland Cement"
- 5) Indian Standard IS-383:1970, "Specifications for Coarse and Fine aggregates".
- 6) IS: 2386 (Part I)-1963 Indian standard – Methods of test for aggregates for concrete - Part IV mechanical properties, Bureau of Indian standard, 1997, New Delhi.
- 7) IS: 4031 (Part 3) – 1988 Indian standard – Methods of physical tests test for hydraulic cement, Bureau of Indian standard, 2002, New Delhi.
- 8) IS:2386 (Part I)-1963 Indian standard ,Methods of test for aggregates for concrete - Part I particle size and shape, Bureau of Indian standard, 1997, New Delhi
- 9) IS: 4031 (Part 4) – 1988 Indian standard "Methods o physical tests test for hydraulic cement – part 4 determination of consistency of standard cement, Bureau of Indian standard, 1988, New Delhi.
- 10) IS: 4031 (Part 5) – 1988 Indian standard – Methods of physical tests test for hydraulic cement – part 5 determination of initial and final setting time of cement, Bureau of Indian standard, 2002, New Delhi.
- 11) IS: 4031 (Part 6) - 1988 Indian standard -Methods of physical tests for hydraulic cement, Bureau of Indian standard, 2003, New Delhi.
- 12) IS: 1199-1959 Indian standards -Methods of sampling and analysis of concrete", Bureau of Indian standard, 1959, New Delhi.
- 13) IS 516 : 1959 Indian standard ,Methods of tests for strength of concrete, Bureau of Indian standard
- 14) Concrete Technology and Practice by M.L. Ghambir.
- 15) Concrete Technology Theory and Practice by M.S. Shetty.

- 16) Neville, A. M., "Concrete Technology", Fourth edition, Pearson Education, New Delhi.
- 17) Siddesh Pai & Kaushik Chandra (2013), "Analysis of Polyester Fiber Reinforced Concrete subjected to elevated temperatures", IJCSEIERD.
- 18) Belkacem Toumiet al., (2010), "Influence of High Temperatures on Surface Cracking of Concrete Studied by Image Scanning Technique".
- 19) D. J. Naus et al., (2005), "Effect of elevated temperature on concrete materials and structures".
- 20) Giassio and Zerbino, "Residual properties of concrete exposed to high temperatures", International conference on concrete technology and structures INCONTEST 2003, KCT, Coimbatore.
- 21) "Study of Behavior of HPC at Elevated Temperatures" by D.P.A. Lakshmi, Dr H. Sudrshan Rao and Smt Vaishali Gorpade faculty JNTU College of Engineering Anantapur.
- 22) "Study on Effects of elevated temperatures on high performance concrete with Metakaolin as admixture" by A.Srinivas.2004 Anantapur
- 23) "Effect of elevated temperatures on High performance concrete with fly ash as admixture". By, Mrs. G. Nagamani, Anantapur.